

Impact of Industrial Chemistry Content Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production among Secondary School Students in Zamfara State

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Abstract

This research is descriptive and experimental using the Hannifen-Peck design model and motivation theory, respectively. The population consists of eighty students, who were randomly selected. A pretest and posttest of the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) is used to determine the achievement, while a structured questionnaire is used to determine the interest and awareness of the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on entrepreneurship skills and acquisition in chalk production among secondary school students in Zamfara State. The structured questionnaire consists of 10 (ten) question items on Interest in the Impact of Industrial Chemistry Concept Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production (IICCKESACP) and 10 (ten) on Awareness of the Impact of Industrial Chemistry Concept Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production (AIICCKESACP). Using the Linkert Scale, statistical tools were used for data analysis. A pilot test was administered to 20 non-participants with reliability coefficients of 0.82, 0.83, and 0.72 for CAT, (IICCKESACP), and (AIICCKESACP), respectively. The null hypothesis stated on the awareness with the mean scores of the respondents of 3.25 and 3.81, which is greater than the decision rule of 2.50, was rejected. From the result, it was concluded that the student was aware and the null was rejected. From the result, it was concluded that the student was aware and had an interest. This result can be used to inform the educational policy of industrial chemistry in secondary school education. This finding can also provide useful insights into the potential of industrial chemistry and entrepreneurship to create job opportunities for secondary school students in the state.

Keyword: Education, Entrepreneurship, Chemistry, Metacognitive, Chalk

Introduction

The economic situation today in our country is becoming unbearable to the citizens. It's not because the government folds its arms; they are also trying to do their best to make everything better for the common citizens, but because the needs and aspirations of the people are beyond the government's capacity to meet them. It's high time for the government to have a total holistic approach by looking into the education content to which every subject is established in order to achieve the stated educational goals. The development of an economy to sustain human problems must have a concerted action policy on different sectors like education, health, and the agricultural system with holistic approaches that foster qualitative and quantitative economic changes. A nation can only develop if a robust and structured education is given that can help in providing solutions to human problems. Education is seen as the tool for the effective integration of individuals into a society so that the individual can achieve self-realization, promote unity, strive for social, economic, political, scientific, cultural, and technological processes, and develop national consciousness. This shows that any nation or country that produces better education for all will be able to meet global competitiveness (Adedo, Umar, & Adesoji 2022).

The inability of the government to meet the yearnings and aspirations of its citizens has now become a treat, leading to unemployment, poverty, and other social crimes, which have now become a canker worm deep in the fabric of every individual just to get a daily bread. These are only some of the intrinsic motivations that can lead people down the path of entrepreneurship or other combinations of reasons that will inspire one to start a business. These developments necessitate the wiliness of every individual to look for education that will suit their demands. The only way out is to integrate entrepreneurship

skills into our teaching and learning in the classroom. Education effectiveness and efficiency during teaching and learning situations in the classroom setting if they must survive, a teacher needs to pay attention to the three teaching and learning domains, which include cognitive, affective, and psychomotor (National Policy on Education 2013). NPE revised in 2013 that it was to promote functional education for skill acquisition, job creation, poverty reduction, and the quality of instruction at all levels of education. Educational institutions perform the significant function of providing learning experiences to lead their students from the darkness of ignorance to the light of knowledge. Efficiency in education is when the aims of educational goals are achieved efficiently and effectively through the stated curriculum contents. The student will become a skilled learner, and that's the only tool to achieve national objectives. Shulman (2007) sees content knowledge as a teacher's achievement, or it's considered a measurable performance indicator for assessing a teacher's achievement. The way out for now is to see how entrepreneurship skill acquisition education will be developed into our teaching within the classroom setting.

The emergence of entrepreneurial education in Nigeria can be attributed to rise in unemployment, crime rate and other social verses due to inappropriate implementation of good policies and bad governance on the utilization of the available resources to meet the yearnings and the aspiration of citizens introduction of entrepreneurship education can serve as substitute in management and utilization of available resources to meet the demanding issues (Nwosu, 2014). Odiagbe and Otemuyiwa (2021) revealed that entrepreneurship education as a learning which involves one towards self-reliance, a reasonable channel that will greatly assist in curbing unemployment and leading to national development if entrepreneurship education is introduced the problem of unemployment will be greatly reduce. If the government pays more attention to skills acquisition and entrepreneurship education is quickly identified and packaged well into trainings, it will serve as substitutes for employment opportunities, reduce crime rate and will also assist individuals to contribute to economic development. Odiagbe and Otemuyiwa (2021) state that entrepreneurship education as a process that involves idea generation, opportunity identification, and business plan, which result in business or product creation. If the country must move forward, this demand for entrepreneurship education must be look into most especially in our secondary school education.

Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN, 2013) give that entrepreneurship education at the senior secondary education level is the teaching and learning at the post basic geared towards inculcating entrepreneurial skills in the learners towards becoming self-reliance. Knowledge acquisition is the process of absorbing and storing new information in memory, the success of which is often gauged by how well the information can later be remembered (retrieved from memory). Guastello, Beasley & Sinatra, (2000) see the process of storing and retrieving information depends heavily on the representation and organization of the information. Moreover, the utility of knowledge can also be influenced by how the information is structured. The most important part of entrepreneurship is that it's a cognitive process using mental approaches where the potential of human knowledge is demonstrated; it's a process where assumption and aspiration can only be established through innovation of mind to become an inventor; sharing of these innovative ideals by interpretation is what it means to be an entrepreneur. Cognitive science shows how concepts are formed in students' minds and, most importantly, how they are connected, which might imply students' conceptual understanding. Ogundeji (2019) states that students' conceptual understanding will continue to require both knowledge of and the ability to use scientific concepts to develop mental models about the way the world operates, following a current scientific theory.

According to Aliu, Kadir, Rasheedat, and Abdulrasaq (2020), metacognition and its related processes have been shown to affect the human performance, functions, and behavior of individuals in an array of situations, including performance in education. Amutha & Sudha (2016) define metacognitive as enabling the learner to detect their weaknesses in learning and determine the better way to learn. One of the aims of education today is to make the student gain the thinking skills and strategies that they will use throughout their lives rather than storing information. The National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP, (2005) states that conceptual understanding in science means understanding the principles of science, especially the concepts used to explain and predict observations of the natural world, and knowing how to apply this understanding efficiently in the design and execution of scientific investigations and in practical reasoning.

The role of secondary education in national educational system cannot be underrated. It is the intermediate level between the primary and tertiary education. As a conciliator, it absorbs the product of primary education, and serves as an input unit for tertiary education being a midpoint in the pecking order of education. Secondary school education indicates its value and its quality influences on the standard of education and shows the level of literacy in the country. (Ogundeji., Umar, Olubunmi & Adedo 2022),

Chemistry is one of the subjects offered at the upper level in Nigerian secondary schools. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) describes chemistry as one of the science subjects that senior secondary school students take. It is a very important science subject and a requirement for further learning in a number of science-related professional courses, like medicine, agriculture, pharmacy, etc. According to Oloyede (2010), chemistry pervades literally every field of human endeavor

and plays a fundamental role in educational advancement. It occupies a unique position among the various science subjects offered at the senior secondary school level because it is a fundamental requirement for most core science-based courses. Tbilisi, (2012) Chemistry as a subject is conceptual. Students learning chemistry at the school level, or in colleges and universities, are taught about and asked to master a wide array of concepts. Concepts are central to understanding chemistry, and the understanding of chemical concepts is therefore a core concern in chemical education. This research was carried out using chalk production as one of the numerous contents in chemistry because it's one of the essential tools that are commonly and widely used in teaching and learning situations and accepted throughout the world. If students are taught to demonstrate it practically in the classroom by transforming chemical combinations into chalk products, it will greatly improve their understanding of scientific principles and phenomena while at the same time serving as skill acquisition, which seduces the researchers. Chalk is a white soft limestone that is formed as a result of the combination of POP (Plaster of Paris) and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) in form of burning limestone that is deposit and develops as coccoliths (a minute calcareous plate created by the decomposition of plankton skeleton), a tiny marine organism. (Evans, Hopson, Royse, & Woods, 2004).

The knowledge acquired in learning chemical concepts is not straightforward and thus requires special training and orientation that would make one carry out the necessary teaching. This has contributed to no interest in or awareness of its importance in daily activities and in the production of common household products. Students at all levels often do not understand or have a partial understanding of the scientific principle behind the knowledge of chemical chemistry concepts or, indeed, misunderstand it when they come across it within the key concepts they meet in their studies of chemistry. This is one of the core issues in chemistry education. The understanding of these scientific concepts and principles behind its operation is certainly still unclear; introducing the student to the aspect of turning chemical contents into products would make some of these concepts and principles behind scientific operation understood.

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the level of awareness on the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State.
2. To examine the level of interest on the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State
3. To determine the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge of achievement on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State

Research Questions

The following proposed research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the level of student awareness of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State?
2. What is the level of student interest in industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State?

Hypotheses

The following Research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge of Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production and student academic achievement among Secondary School students in Zamfara State.
2. There is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method.
3. There is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production in Zamfara State

Methodology

This research is descriptive and experimental using the Hannifen-Peck design model and motivation theory, respectively. The state has fourteen local governments, which are divided into three senatorial councils: Zamfara Central Zone, Zamfara West, and Zamfara North. One senatorial council was selected using simple random sampling. The senatorial councils consist of different local government areas, which include Zamfara Central Zone with four local government areas, Zamfara North Zone with four local government areas, and Zamfara West Zone with six local government areas. Out of the selected senatorial councils, two local government areas were selected using a multistage process. Selection of two schools each from the selected local government area using purposeful selection based on the availability of the laboratory and students offering chemistry as part of their science subject. The population for this study comprised all science senior secondary schools in

Zamfara, with a random sampling of 80 (eighty) senior secondary school (SSS I) students that offered chemistry subjects drawn from four public senior science secondary schools in Zamfara Central Zone in the Gusau Local Government area of Zamfara State. A pretest and posttests on Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) is used to determine the achievement while a structured questionnaire were used to determine the interest and awareness on the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. The structured questionnaire consists of 10 (Ten) question items on Interest of the Impact of Industrial Chemistry Concept Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production (IIICCKESACP) and 10 (Ten) on Awareness of the Impact of Industrial Chemistry Concept Knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition in Chalk Production (AIICCKESACP). Using Linkert Scale, statistical tools were used for data analysis, A pilot test was administered to 20 non participant with the reliability coefficient of 0.82, 0.83 and 0.72 were obtained for CAT, (IIICCKESACP) and (AIICCKESACP) respectively.

Results

Research Questions

What is the level of student awareness of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on level of students' awareness

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
Are you aware that the production of some non-consumable products is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.60	.704	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of some consumable product is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.25	.948	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of some technological equipment's made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.37	.919	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of some home appliances and equipment's is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.26	.910	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of chalk is made through transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.59	.774	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of chalk is made from combinations of some elements through transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.84	.462	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of kampala is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.63	.663	Accepted
Are you aware that kampala design products is made from combination of some elements through transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.71	.508	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of herbicide in insect killer products is made from transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.81	.480	Accepted
Are you aware that the production of herbicide in insect killer is made from combination of some elements through transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.72	.595	Accepted

From the result in table one, what is the level of awareness of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. The mean of the respondents is between 3.25 and 3.81 which is greater than decision rule of 2.50. This was subjected to descriptive analysis it's here by concluded that student were aware, This show that there is no practical demonstration of most industrial chemistry content teaching that could hinder more explanation to scientific principles for better understanding.

Research Question 2

What is the level of interest in industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State?

Table 2: Descriptive statistics showing level of Interest of Secondary School Students on Industrial Chemistry Contents

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
Teaching practical production of insect killer in the classroom will help to increase student learning interest in in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.80	.461	Accepted
Teaching practical production of chalk in the classroom will help to increase student learning interest in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content.	3.79	.520	Accepted
Teaching practical production of kampala in the classroom will help to increase student learning interest in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.79	.495	Accepted
Use of practical method to teach some chemistry chemical concept in the classroom will help student learning interest in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content	3.69	.608	Accepted
Use of practical method to teach some chemistry chemical concept in the classroom will increase student entrepreneurial interest	3.64	.621	Accepted
Exposing student to use of knowledge in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content on consumable products production increases student learning interest in chemistry as a subject	3.48	.763	Accepted
Exposing student to use of knowledge in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content on non-consumable products production increases student learning interest in chemistry as a subject	3.55	.692	Accepted
Practical teaching on how to transform industrial chemistry chemical content to product will assist and expose student to element's familiarization leading to an increase in student learning interest of entrepreneurial concept	3.69	.493	Accepted
Exposing student to use of knowledge in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content production increases student learning interest in chemistry entrepreneurial concept	3.54	.728	Accepted
Exposing student to use of knowledge in transforming industrial chemistry chemical content production improve student learning understanding in chemistry entrepreneurial concept	3.56	.709	Accepted

From the result in table two, what is the level of student interest in industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. The Mean score of the respondents is between 3.54 and 3.80 which is greater than decision rule of 2.50. This was subjected to descriptive analysis it's here by concluded that student have interest of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. This shows that student have interest in entrepreneurship skills acquisition.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge of Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production and student academic achievement among Secondary School students in Zamfara State.

Table 3: t-test on student academic achievement

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig	Mean Difference
Pretest	80	25.38	8.998	25.222	.000	25.375
Posttest	80	55.05	27.950	17.617	.000	55.050

From the result in table three, there is no significant difference in students' achievement on the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. This was subjected to T-test analysis. From the result it was observed that there is positive increase on student academic achievement the mean scores of pretests 25.38 the posttest mean scores is 55.05 with mean difference of 25.375 and significance level of .000 lesser than 0.05. It is concluded that the null hypotheses is here by rejected there is significance influence in student academic achievement.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method.

Table 4 Group mean of experimental and control

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pretest	experimental	40	29.38	6.732	1.064
	Control	40	21.38	9.267	1.465
Posttest	experimental	40	76.95	17.548	2.775
	Control	40	33.15	17.048	2.696

From the result in table four, there is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method. This was subjected to descriptive analysis. this show the difference in the performance of each group based on experimental and the control group in the pretest, the mean score of experimental is 29.38 with standard deviation 6.732 and the mean scores for the control is 21.38 with standard deviation 9.267 while in the posttest mean score of experimental is 76.95 with standard deviation 17.548 and the mean score control is 33.15 with standard deviation 17.048. The mean difference between the pretest and posttest of experimental group is 47.57 while that of control difference between the pretest and posttest is 11.77. There is influence on the academic achievement for experimental group than the convectional group.

Table 5: ANCOVA of students Achievement in Chemistry Chemical Contents

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	50300.355 ^a	2	25150.177	169.674	.000
Intercept	1920.861	1	1920.861	12.959	.001
Pretest	11931.555	1	11931.555	80.495	.000
Group	15958.406	1	15958.406	107.662	.000
Error	11413.445	77	148.227		
Total	304154.000	80			
Corrected Total	61713.800	79			

The result from table five, there is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method. This was subjected to ANCOVA analysis of covariance. The mean square value of the group is 15958.406 with .000 level of significant lesser than the p-value at 0.05. This implies that there is significant influence of the group achievement when taught with it and does taught with conventional method of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State The null hypothesis is here by rejected at 0.05 level of significant and concluded that there is significant influence on the group on industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production in Zamfara State.

Table 6: ANCOVA of gender influence

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	37198.274 ^a	2	18599.137	58.417	.000
Intercept	774.903	1	774.903	2.434	.123
Pretest	37030.074	1	37030.074	116.307	.000
Gender	2856.325	1	2856.325	8.971	.004
Error	24515.526	77	318.383		
Total	304154.000	80			
Corrected Total	61713.800	79			

The result from table 6, there is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production in Zamfara State. This was subjected to analysis of covariance the mean square value of the group is 2856.325 with .004 level of significant lesser than the p-value at 0.05. This implies that there is significant influence of the gender on industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State The null hypothesis is here by rejected at 0.05 level of significant and concluded that there is significant influence of gender on industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production.

Discussion of Findings

There is no significant impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge of Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in Chalk Production and student academic achievement among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. The result of the analysis of hypothesis shows that there was significant impact of the content knowledge on chalk production the hypothesis is rejected. This is in line with Syden and Gordon (2014), who conducted a study to analyze the entrepreneurial awareness among

high school students. A sample of 150 high school and higher secondary school students from 6 schools were selected for the study. The result revealed that majority of the respondents heard about entrepreneurship and it suggests that entrepreneurship education can create awareness from the school level itself so that self-employment career option can instill at the earlier. According to Verheul and Stel (2007) increase in education level of entrepreneurs leads to an increase in entrepreneurial income and productivity. Moreover, education is claimed to be an important factor when starting entrepreneurial activity. This shows that a good ability to turn ideas into action make individual aware and understand the chemistry chemical content of their work and able to seize opportunities that's available for new acquisition.

There is no significant difference in achievement of students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production and those taught using conventional method. The result of the analysis of hypothesis shows that there was significant difference on chemistry students' achievement when taught using industrial chemistry content knowledge and does taught without using it for entrepreneurship skills acquisition among secondary school students in Zamfara State the hypothesis is rejected. The result was in line with related study by Malebana (2014) showed that students were more pulled rather than pushed into entrepreneurship. In other words, students were interested in entrepreneurship mainly as a result of positive factors such as the opportunity to make use of creative talents, independence and prospects for higher earnings than through negative factors such as high prevalence of unemployment. Olatunbosun (2019) observed that science practical work plays a vital role in developing scientific knowledge and enhancing scientific skills, attitude and enquiry based learning that student learn by performing concrete activities by comparing experimental activities to normal learning this have an effect on learning achievement This shows that it's not unemployment that leads to entrepreneurship but for self-reliance.

There is no significant difference in achievement of male and female students exposed to entrepreneurship skills acquisition on chalk production in Zamfara State The result of the analysis shows that there was significant influence of the gender on industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State the hypothesis is also rejected. The result is in line with Asoegwu (2008) observed from it study breaking gender barrier on performance in science, he used hand-on and minds-on science that students either male or female that were expose to scientific process oriented learning, students engagement, manipulation of materials assist in problem solving skill in respect of the gender., while Duyilemi and Olusa (2016) gender and performance, in their experiment discover that there is no significant difference in performance of male and female performance in science subject.

Conclusion

The result shows that the student were aware and they have interest of the impact of industrial chemistry content knowledge on Entrepreneurship Skills-Acquisition in chalk Production among Secondary School students in Zamfara State. It also observed that the student taught with the practical demonstration using industrial chemistry content knowledge have better achievement in entrepreneurship skills acquisition than those taught with conventional methods its concluded that gender and academic achievement is influenced by entrepreneurship skills acquisition this will gear up student interest and give more awareness with better understanding to scientific principle which in turns boost student academic achievement and reduce the rate of unemployment and social crimes.

Recommendations

1. Government need to look into how curriculum content of every course can be attained and
2. Government need holistic approach to the type of education needed to its citizen that would lead to reduction in unemployment and social crimes.
3. Both the government and the stake holders in education to create more awareness on the need to transform most of the contents that will serve as entrepreneurship skills acquisition.
4. The teacher in chemistry and other science related course for more training.
5. Adequate finance must be put in place proper implementation of the skill to survive.
6. Teacher of sciences must see skill acquisition beyond the out the school curriculum.

References

- Adedo G. A, Umar, S. & Adesoji, O. O. (2022) Repositioning science teacher education through practical oriented application in the teaching and learning process for Glob IJSGS *International journal of science for global sustainability* 8(4):91 – 98.
- Adedo, G. A., Jimoh I. Y, & Salman S. I. (2018). Promoting quality science education learning for good governance and sustainable development. *Journal of School of Science Education* 1(1):81 – 89.

- Aliu, A., Kadir, R. B. & Abdulrasaq, O. A. Relationship (2020). Between Senior Secondary school students' metacognitive attitude and their academic performance in physics *International journal of scientific & Engineering Research* 11(6): 260 – 265.
- Amutha, S. & Sudha, A. (2016). Metacognitive Awareness of tertiary level chemistry. *Caribbean journal of science and technology* 4 914 – 919. Retrived from <http://caribjstech.com>.
- Evans, D. J., Hopson, P. M., Royse, K. R., & Woods, M. A. (2004). A geological model of the chalk of the east kent, Brithis Geological Survey Commissioned report Cr/04/092.
- Federal Government of Nigeria (2013). *National Policy on Education* 4rd Edition. NERDC press Lagos.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) National Policy on Education, Lagos Federal Government press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2014). *National Policy on Education*. NERC Press.
- Guastello, F., Beasley, M. and Sinatra, R. (2000). Concept Mapping Effects on Science Content Comprehension of Low-Achieving Inner-City Seventh Graders. *Rase: Remedial and Special Education* (21):356–365.
- National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) (2005). *Science Conceptual Understanding*. Retrieved from <http://nces.ed.gov/nationsreportcard>.
- Odiabge, S. I & Otemuyiwa. B. T. (2021). Instructional strategies for teaching entrepreneurship subject in secondary school in the federal capital territory Abuja Nigeria *AAUA journal of science and technology Education* 3(2):122 – 133.
- Ogundeji, O. M., Madu, B. C., & Onuya, C. C. (2019). Scientific explanation of phenomena and concept formation as correlates of students' understanding of physics concepts. *European Journal of Physics Education*. 10 (3):10 – 19.
- Ogundeji.O., Umar, H. B., Olubunmi, A. O. & Adedo, G. A. (2022). Influence of class size and school location on students' level of conceptual understanding in secondary school chemistry *Zamfara International Journal of Education (ZIJE)* 2(1):2814 – 1369.
- Ohadiugha, M. N. (2021). Impact of experience and gender on the teachers acquisition of ICT skills for effective implementation of senior secondary school curriculum in federal capital territory FCT Abuja *AAUA Journal of Science and Technology Education* 3(2):63 – 73.
- Oloyede, I. O. (2010). Enhanced mastery learning strategy on the schievement and Self- concept in senior secondary school chemistry *Humanity and Social Sciences Journal* 5(1):19–24.
- Shulman, L. S. (2007). Knowlegde and teaching foundation of new reform. *Havard Educational review*, 57(1) 1 – 22.
- Tbilisi, G. (2012). Student active searning in science collection of papers salis final conference 29-30 August, 2012 Iliia State University Tbilisi, Isbn 978-9941-18-117-7 Iliia State University Press 3/5 cholokashvili ave, tbilisi, 0162, Georgia.